

The Evil Clouds of ICT: An Analysis

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Abstract

In this digital era, ICT plays a vital role in every walk of life. Both Government as well as private sectors utilizes these advanced technologies for bringing out effective outcomes. As far as education field is considered, ICT plays a tremendous role in the aspect of teachers as well as students. It had revolutionized earlier modes of teaching strategies like teacher centered method etc. This is the time to deal with digital learning, robotic learning and hence talk and chalk method gets faded as time proceeds. Even, the old traditional classrooms comprising of rich cultural memories gets vanished because of digital arousements. As we all mainly focused on the positive impact created by these ICT tools, there are some of the tedious hidden issues which also need our attention. The evil shadows fall on physical, psychological as well as sociological dimensions either directly or indirectly. Being literates, we must focus on the ways and means by which ICT can be enabled and enhanced in a right channel to reach the unreached domains along with the ways of monitoring and suppressing the evil issues aroused.

Keywords: Tremendous, digital learning, robotic learning.

Introduction

Information and communication technology plays a vital role in every walk of life. Both Government as well as private sectors utilizes these advanced technologies for bringing out effective outcomes. As far as education field is considered, ICT plays a tremendous role in the aspect of teachers as well as students. It had revolutionized earlier modes of teaching strategies like teacher centered method etc. This is the time to deal with digital learning, robotic learning and hence talk and chalk method gets faded as time proceeds. Even, the old traditional classrooms comprising of rich cultural memories gets vanished because of digital arousements. As we all mainly focused on the positive impact created by these ICT tools, there are some of the tedious hidden issues which also need our attention. The evil shadows fall on physical, psychological as well as sociological dimensions either directly or indirectly. Being literates, we must focus on the ways and means by which ICT can be enabled and enhanced in a right channel to reach the unreached domains along with the ways of monitoring and suppressing the evil issues aroused.

Evils of ICT

Good and bad are the two consequences of all the universal happenings especially to technology. Modernisation, commercialisation, privatisation, industrialisation, liberalisation and globalisation revolutionise our present world beyond our expectations. Eventhough, we face many discomforts by using ICT.

Adults nowadays suffers from effects of technology on youth such as physical effects, psychological side and sociological side

1. Physical effects

- Lack of social relationships
- Social isolation
- Obesity
- Depression
- Poor sleep habit
- stress and strain
- Back ache, wrist ache, head ache
- Vision problems

2. Psychological effects

- shortened attention
- emotional swing
- addiction

3. Sociological effects

- lack of social boundary
- more time wasted
- distracted from goals
- E-waste
- lack of privacy
- e-harassments’
- violence

Depression is the situation which lacks in joy depression is the most common worldwide illness nowadays. When we compare men and woman, women suffer a bit higher. Due to the electronic gadgets addiction, adults nowadays suffer from insomnia (difficulty in sleeping) or hypersomnia (excessive sleeping).

Stress is an umbrella term which includes psychologic (mental) and physiologic (bodily) imbalance felt by the people. There are two kinds of stress such as good and bad. Good stress arises when we gain something. It acts as a motivator for the development of the individual. Negative stress arouses when a person faces social, physical, organisational and emotional problems. There are many causes for stress such as poor working conditions, lack of interaction with peers, organisational changes, lack of social support, during conflict period, when we try to balance between demands and reality, during workloads etc.,The keyfactor of stress is “how we response to the physical and emotional changes” around us. The thing which needs serious attention is, by means of regular practices, yoga, flexibility and when we love the thing we do, we can easily manage stress on our day to day life.

Hacking has its own definition such as the way by which information of other individual get accessed without any prior permission. The purpose of hackers may vary such as for fun or to steal information or to destroy their resources etc., the modes of hacking includes email, online banking, computer, network, website hacking etc. we are only responsible for our accounts we have. It’s our duty to maintain it with safety protocols by including characters, digits etc.,

As we see our daily newspapers, the articles related to harassments’ goes on increasing. Sexual harassment is nothing but the unwelcome sexual habits or requests for sexual factors or anyother unwanted conduct. When we look deeper, it is evident that, the knowledge of sex education does not reach the adults or whomever involved in these kinds of activities.

Eye discomfort occurs during the over usage of eye muscles. Also rending over concentration on tasks such as working on computers, reading during travelling or watching electronic gadgets over a long period of time etc., contribute to eye strain. Nowadays computer vision syndrome (CVS), which is the combination of eye strain and body muscle strain during the computer usage is seen common among adults. The recovery measures include, blinking our eyes in the regular period of time, reduce the brightness of the display screen, take short relaxation in between, going for regular check-ups etc.

There was a time in which Indians are rich in contact between an individual and the society. Social isolation is a serious issue that includes individuals of any age especially youngsters. It may have a wider range of symptoms such as staying home for longer periods of time, lack of communication with their family and peers, avoiding contact with other humans such as friends etc., nowadays social isolation had become chronic which is the potential cause for majority of our emotional or psychological challenges.

Next major issue is obesity in which the accumulation of the excess body fat occurs. Studies reveals that the major cause for obesity is excessive intake of food, lack of physical activity and genetic susceptibility.

Electric and electronic devices which when left unused becomes E-waste. The thing to be noted is, E-waste contains many harmful, toxic products which directly affects the health of the individual.

Nowadays, even kids are addicted to mobile and computer games. As the concept of game developers are more concerned about violence, the players are pushed to indulge those concepts in their mind. Another issue with ICT is, computer addiction by which excessive use of the computer persists.

Remedial Measures

Educational boards must try to include the impact of technology in the day to day activities. Regarding gadgets addiction, there are many strategies for avoiding computer usage such as limiting the usage time, sharing our ideas with other friends/well-wishers, encouraging adductors to seek professional counselling, diverting them to read books or spend more time in hobbies etc.,

The positive approach for E-waste management is to emphasize on 3R’s such as Reduce, Reuse and Recycle. We should be aware of the energy balance between calories consumed and used.

Conclusion

Technology evils will not only affect our present generations but also our future generations. Teachers play a significant role in shaping the citizens of India rich in moral and ethical values, constructive thoughts and a humans’ rich in social responsibility. We can cascade our knowledge to students either by oral or by means of technology. But the thing to be noted is, if technology is being used for delivering, try to blend our tradition and technology. Include values and morals whenever possible. We must remember olden educational practices like Gurukula system in which student obey teachers’,gained more knowledge from their teachers and implement those values in their day to day life. Knowledge shared by teacher retained in the hearts of students. But the

things going on in our present generation is upside down. They just remembered or studied for namesake, try to crack exams for updating their degree status. These kinds of happenings lead to the doubtfulness of the moral and ethical values hidden below.

So teachers should make ICT as a tool in their hands for enhancing the teaching learning process. it is our soul responsibility to use technology to solve our problems. only then our Indian education system flourish still further.